

Notes on Contributors

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Luminița Hoarță Cărăușu:

- Professor, Ph.D., Romanian Language and General Linguistics Department, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, Romania;
- author of 12 books, 2 courses of lectures, 63 articles and investigations published in Romania and abroad;
- participant in national and international scientific conferences;
- member of national and international research teams and associations;
- member of Honorary Board of *Speech and Context* International Journal of Linguistics, Semiotics and Literary Science;
- led a series of courses in a number of prestigious universities from Germany: Konstanz University, Saarland University, Friedrich Schiller University (Jena) etc.;
- guides doctoral theses;
- manager of research projects (*Pragmatics of Pronoun, A Corpus of Contemporary Spoken Romanian* etc.);
- member of the research teams within some projects (*Colloquial language in Romance area. A Pragmalinguistic Synchronic and Diachronic Study*);
- organizer of scientific conferences;
- member of the Defense Board of Doctoral Theses;
- research areas: syntax and morphology of Romanian, linguistic pragmatics, persuasive strategies in political and publicistic discourses.

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- author of significant scientific and didactic publications;
- organiser or co-organiser of important scientific conferences;
- participant in national and international scientific conferences;
- member of the Romanian Society of Dialectological Sciences, the Society for Name Studies in Britain and Ireland (SNSBI), the American Name Society (ANS), the International Council of Onomastic Sciences (ICOS), the Société de Linguistique Romane (SLiR), the International Association for Dialogue Analysis (IADA), the Society of Classical Studies, the Names Society of Southern Africa (NSA);
- supervisor of doctoral theses;
- member of various panels of expert examiners appointed to award the “Doctor of Philology” degree;
- scientific referee or linguistic advisor for various volumes (*Numele și numirea. Actele Conferinței Internaționale de Onomastică „Numele și numirea”, ediția a III-a: Convențional/ neconvențional în onomastică, Baia Mare, 1 aprilie 2015, Oliviu Felecan (ed.), Cluj-Napoca, Editura Mega/Editura Argonaut, 2015; Numele și numirea. Actele Conferinței Internaționale de Onomastică „Numele și numirea”, ediția a II-a: Onomastica din spațiul public actual, Baia Mare, 9-11 mai 2013, Oliviu Felecan (ed.), Cluj-Napoca, Editura Mega/Editura Argonaut, 2013 etc.);*
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